

Effect Of Pilates Vs. Chair Aerobics on Physical Activity in Desktop Working Women with Dysmenorrhea

Lawrence Fernandes*

Assistant Professor, D.Y. Patil College of Physiotherapy, D.Y. Patil Education Society (Deemed to be university), Kolhapur, 416003

ABSTRACT

Background: Dysmenorrhea being one of the most prevalent gynaecological disorders affecting women of reproductive age and is characterized by excruciating menstrual cramps that may hamper everyday activities, sleep quality and physical wellbeing. Dysmenorrhea is a widespread problem among professional women that have sedentary lifestyle with prevalence 50 to 90 % worldwide. Whereas Pilates emphasizes on core development, posture and controlled breathing while on the other hand Chair Aerobics promotes low impact aerobic exercises that can enhance circulation and levels of physical activity. However there are limited studies that have been compared to physical activity in desktop working women in dysmenorrhea. **Aims of the study:** To study the effect of Pilates vs. chair aerobics on physical activity in working women with Dysmenorrhea. **Procedure:** Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethical committee. A total of 46 participants meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected and were randomly divided into two groups .Group A (23 participants) received Pilates and Group B (23 participants) received chair aerobics exercises for 4 weeks . **Outcome measures:** Numeric Pain Rating Scale, International Physical Activity Questionnaire. **Result:** Effect of Group A was assessed using Paired t –test / Wilcoxon’s Signed Rank Test and effect of Group B was also assessed using Paired t –test / Wilcoxon’s Signed Rank Test. Comparison between both groups was done using Unpaired t –test / Mann – Whitney Test . The results indicated statistically significant improvement within both groups for all outcome measures. However, Group a (Pilates) showed greater improvement than Group B (Chair Aerobics). **Conclusion:** Both Pilates and Chair Aerobics exercises were effective in reducing pain , improving physical activity in desktop working women , yet Pilates were found more effective than Chair Aerobics .

Keywords: Dysmenorrhea, Pilates, Chair Aerobics, Physical Activity, Numeric Pain Rating Scale, International Physical Activity Questionnaire.

INTRODUCTION

Dysmenorrhea also called as painful menstruation is defined as intense, painful and cramping sensation felt in the lower abdomen often accompanied by additional symptoms which includes sweating, headache, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea and tremulousness which occurs just prior or during the menses ⁽¹⁾. However, a more pragmatic and realistic definition encompasses instances of menstrual discomfort severe enough to interfere with daily activity. ⁽³⁾ Dysmenorrhea is categorized into two distinct types Primary Dysmenorrhea and Secondary Dysmenorrhea based on whether identifiable etiology is present. ⁽²⁾ Primary Dysmenorrhea is characterized

by lower abdominal pain that travels to the thigh and lower back and lacks and evident pelvic disease. ⁽³⁾ Secondary Dysmenorrhea is marked by dull ache often accompanied by dyspareunia, infertility and menstrual disorders. ⁽⁴⁾ While the exact cause of primary dysmenorrhea is unknown, uterine muscle ischemia a state that is brought by excessive contraction of the muscles during menstruation is thought to be the pathophysiological cause of this condition. ⁽⁵⁾ Decreased in progesterone hormone throughout the luteal phase and excess production of prostaglandins and inflammatory factors are believed as the result of ischemia and hypoxia of the uterus

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

causing dysmenorrhea individuals to experience aggravated pain.⁽⁵⁾ Based on previously published studies, dysmenorrhea lowers the ability of school-age adolescents and young women from a variety of social and cultural backgrounds to focus, participate, and use test-taking strategies, which negatively affects their overall academic performance.⁽⁶⁾ Activity limitation and absence from work, school or college are linked to severe dysmenorrhea.⁽⁷⁾ There aren't many research on dysmenorrhea in working women, though. Dysmenorrhea in working women is correlated with workplace related characteristics, such as working hours that correlates with the menstrual symptoms and productivity and job related stressors such as lack of job control, fewer peer support and insecure employment at work.⁽¹⁴⁾ An adverse effect on participation in everyday activities is observed in 5-20% of women.⁽⁷⁾ In some research, dysmenorrhea and monthly pain are treated interchangeably, with prevalence rates ranging from 15% to 95% and menstrual pain varied from minor to inhibiting day-to-day functioning.⁽¹⁴⁾ Pilates which is referred as mind body workout emphasizes breathing and while promoting appropriate posture, muscle strength, flexibility and trunk stability.⁽⁵⁾ Through controlled movement performed on a mat, Pilates promotes flexibility and strengthens muscles boosting both mental and physical wellbeing.⁽¹²⁾ Throughout each Pilates exercise, the abdominal area is constantly used, acting as the technique's main strength core.⁽⁸⁾ Pilates exercise improves physical fitness and health by increasing muscular strength endurance, flexibility and cardio respiratory endurance and they additionally possess a good impact on female sex hormones.⁽¹²⁾ Exercises can have a hormonal influence on the uterus lining or elevate the amount of endorphins in the bloodstreams.⁽⁹⁾ Exercise is referred to increase the brain's endorphin production which raises the threshold towards pain and has been observed to elevate the mood of those who engage in it.⁽¹⁰⁾ Chair aerobics exercise is a type of physical activity that is done while seated, and it mainly relies on the process of aerobic energy generation.⁽¹¹⁾ Enhanced blood circulation from aerobic activity relieves pain.⁽⁴⁾ Chair based exercises are especially advantageous as a training method since they minimize load bearing, reduce balance issues in people with particularly poor mobility and stabilizes the lower spine by providing a fixed base. They also

permit for a greater range of movement by providing points of leverage and support.⁽¹³⁾ For people who lead sedentary lifestyles or are employed in sedentary surroundings, chair aerobics is a great substitute to active exercise.⁽¹³⁾

METHODOLOGY

An Analytical Interventional Study done by using Probability method and Simple Random Sampling. The study conducted on Desktop Working Women at Yoga Lab, D. Y. Patil College of Physiotherapy, Kadamwadi, Kolhapur for a duration of 6 Months. The study started after getting ethical approval from Institutional Ethics Committee. Study subjects fulfilling exclusion and inclusion criteria were selected for study. The Sample Size was 46

Inclusion Criteria- Working Women from 30-40 years, desk job working women's with 6 hours work scheduled, working 5 days a week, dysmenorrhea diagnosed by a Gynaecologist

Exclusion Criteria- Secondary Dysmenorrhea with active pathology of endometriosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, ovarian cysts, fibroids, Infections such as Urinary tract infection and sexually transmitted diseases.

PROCEDURE

Ethical clearance was obtained from the institution ethical committee. Prior written consent form from the participants was obtained. Pre assessment value were recorded before the study was started. The participants were divided into two group i.e. Group A and Group B including 23 participants in each group. Participants were educated about the condition and procedure of the exercise was explained in detail. Group A received Pilates exercise for 4 weeks, and Group B received Chair Aerobics exercises for 4 weeks. Data collected on all study variables was entered MS Excel to prepare the Master sheet. Pre and post assessment of pain and sleep quality was done for each participant of each group using Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI). The parameters were assessed before and after the intervention period for all participants.

Group A (PILATES) :

The exercises will be performed on a mat under supervision.

1The Hundred

2Single leg stretch

3Leg circles

4Bridging

5Spine stretch

6Swan

7Double leg stretch

8Roll up

Each exercises will be demonstrated to the participants and they will be instructed perform movements slowly with controlled breathing.

Group B (CHAIR AEROBICS):

Participants in Group B will perform Chair Aerobics exercises which are low impact aerobic exercises performed while sitting on a chair. Chair Aerobics help improve blood circulation, increase physical activity, and reduce muscular tension associated with dysmenorrhea.

Exercises will be performed using a chair for support.

1Knee Lift

2Diagonal toe touch

3Lunges

4Punches

5Flick Kicks

6Half Jack

7Criss Cross

Each exercises will be explained and demonstrated to the participants before performing.

RESULT

The comparative study of effect of Pilates exercises and Chair Aerobics Exercises on sleep Quality, Physical Activity in desktop working women in Dysmenorrhea shows that both exercises were equally effective in reducing pain and improving physical activity using outcome measures (NPRS and IPAQ). Therefore, Pilates exercises is been more effective than chair Aerobics in reducing pain and improving Physical Activity in Desktop working women.

Age Distribution

Here the minimum age of the desktop working women is considered to be 24 years old whereas maximum age to be considered is 35 years old.

The Standard Deviation is 2.491.

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	24	35	27.87	2.491

Pre And Post Values In Group A

The table presents the pre and post values of Numerical Pain Rating Scale and International physical activity questionnaire in **GROUP A**. For the Numerical Pain Rating Scale, the mean pre intervention score was 7.09 with Std. Deviation 0.73 and the post intervention score reduced to 2.70 with Std. Deviation 0.56 showing a significant reduction in

pain intensity. The statistical analysis revealed p-value < 0.001.

For the, International physical activity questionnaire the mean pre intervention score was 1363.48 with Std. Deviation 84.89 and the post intervention score was increased to 2789.13 with Std. Deviation 262.61 showing a considerable increase in physical activity levels. The statistical analysis revealed p-value < 0.001.

Group A				
Parameters	Assessment Period	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Numerical Pain Rating Scale	Pre	7.09	0.73	<0.001*
	Post	2.70	0.56	
International physical activity questionnaire	Pre	1363.48	84.89	<0.001*
	Post	2789.13	262.61	

Fig 1

Fig 2

Pre And Post Values In Group B

The table presents the pre and post values of Numerical Pain Rating Scale and International physical activity questionnaire in **GROUP B**.

For the Numerical Pain Rating Scale the mean pre intervention score was 7.04 with Std. Deviation 0.77 and the post intervention score reduced to 4.43 with

Std. Deviation 0.51 showing a significant reduction in pain intensity. The statistical analysis revealed p-value < 0.001

For the, International physical activity questionnaire the mean pre intervention score was 1357.83 with Std. Deviation 91.00 and the post intervention score was increased to 2166.35 with Std. Deviation 129.84

showing a considerable increase in physical activity levels. The statistical analysis revealed p-value < 0.001.

Group B				
Parameters	Assessment Period	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Numerical Pain Rating Scale	Pre	7.04	0.77	<0.001*
	Post	4.43	0.51	
International physical activity questionnaire	Pre	1357.83	91.00	<0.001*
	Post	2166.35	129.84	

Comaprison Of Group A And Group B

The group comparison analysis demonstrated statistically significant differences between Group A and Group B. across all measured parameters. For Numerical Pain Rating Scale, Group A showed a lower mean score of 2.07 with Std. Deviation 0.56, whereas Group B had a higher mean score of 4.43 with Std. Deviation 0.51 which shows there is pain

reduction in **Group A**. For International Physical Activity Questionnaire, Group A had a higher mean score of 2789.13 with Std. Deviation 262.61, while Group B had a mean score of 2166.35 with Std. Deviation 129.84, which shows there is increased physical activity in **Group A**.

All the observed differences were highly statistically significant (< 0.001), indicating that intervention in **Group A was more Effective than Group B.**

Group Comparison				
Parameters	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Numerical Pain Rating Scale	A	2.70	0.56	<0.001*
	B	4.43	0.51	
International physical activity questionnaire	A	2789.13	262.61	<0.001*
	B	2166.35	129.84	

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to compare the effectiveness of Pilates exercises and Chair Aerobics exercises on pain and physical activity levels in desktop working women with dysmenorrhea. A total of 46 participants aged between 24 and 35 years were equally divided into two groups: Group A received Pilates exercises and Group B received Chair Aerobics exercises for a duration of four weeks. The outcome measures used were the Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) and the

International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ). Dysmenorrhea is one of the most common gynaecological disorders affecting women of reproductive age and is frequently associated with reduced work productivity, decreased participation in physical activities, and limitations in daily functioning. Previous studies have reported prevalence rates ranging from 15% to 95%, indicating its significant impact on women’s health and quality of life (1,14). Severe dysmenorrhea is often linked with absenteeism from work and decreased physical

performance (7). In the present study, both Group A and Group B demonstrated statistically significant improvements in pain reduction and physical activity levels following the intervention period ($p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that exercise-based interventions are effective non-pharmacological strategies for the management of dysmenorrhea. The improvement observed in both groups may be attributed to increased blood circulation, enhanced endorphin release, reduction in muscular tension, and improved hormonal regulation associated with regular physical activity (9,10,13). Group A (Pilates exercises) has proven to be showing greater improvement in pain reduction compared to group B (Chair Aerobics Exercises). The mean NPRS score in Group A reduced from 7.09 to 2.70, whereas Group B showed a reduction from 7.04 to 4.43. Pilates focuses on controlled breathing, core strengthening, postural control, flexibility and trunk stability, which may be considered to contribute to improved pelvic muscle function and decreased pain perception. These findings are consistent with the studies conducted by Soni and Desai (2021) and Khadiga et al. (2019), who was the one who reported significant reduction in pain intensity and improvement in quality of life following Pilates intervention in women with primary dysmenorrhea(10,12). Following the intervention, both groups IPAQ scores significantly improved in terms of physical activity levels. However, the Pilates group showed more pronounced improvements. The mean IPAQ score in Group A increased from 1363.48 to 2789.13, while in Group B it increased from 1357.83 to 2166.35. Pilates exercises are proven to improve muscular strength, endurance, flexibility and overall functional capacity, thereby enabling individuals to participate more actively in daily activities and exercise routines. Previous studies have also demonstrated that structured exercise programs are beneficial in improving physical fitness and reducing dysmenorrhea related symptoms (11,13). Chair Aerobics exercises also produced notable improvements in both pain reduction and physical activity. These exercises are low impact aerobic activities performed in a seated position and are particularly beneficial for individuals with sedentary lifestyles or limited mobility. The improvements observed in Group B may be attributed to enhanced blood circulation, reduction in muscle stiffness and increased aerobic endurance resulting from regular

chair based movements. Studies by Berde et al. (2019) and Sakpal and Patil (2023) also reported positive effects of chair aerobics in reducing dysmenorrhea symptoms and improving functional activity levels (4,14). All outcome indicators showed statistically significant differences in favour of Pilates group when the two groups were compared ($p < 0.001$). These results imply that while both therapies are beneficial, Pilates could provide more advantageous because of its all-encompassing strategy that include breathing control, core stabilization, increased flexibility and mind body synchronization. Additionally, Pilates may enhance muscular balance and posture, which may lessen the stress and discomfort brought on by dysmenorrhea. The overall enhancement shown in both groups emphasizes how crucial regular exercise is for managing dysmenorrhea. Exercises is known to boost blood flow, raise endorphin production, lower prostaglandin levels, and lessen pain perception, all of which enhance physical health and functional abilities. (10,13). The findings of the present study are consistent with the comparative study conducted by Bhatt et al. (2024), which concluded that both Pilates and Chair Aerobics are effective in managing menstrual symptoms, with Pilates demonstrating greater effectiveness(2). Therefore, the present study concludes that both Pilates and Chair Aerobics exercises are effective non pharmacological interventions for reducing pain and improving physical activity levels in desktop working women with dysmenorrhea. However, Pilates exercises were found to be more effective than Chair Aerobics exercises in achieving these outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The present study was conducted to compare the effect of Pilates exercises and Chair Aerobics exercises on pain and physical activity in desktop working women with dysmenorrhea. The findings of the study revealed that both interventions were effective in reducing pain intensity and improving physical activity levels among the participants. Statistically significant improvements were observed within both the groups for all outcome measures following the four week intervention period. However, when both groups were compared, Pilates exercises demonstrated greater effectiveness in reducing pain and enhancing physical activity levels

compared to Chair Aerobics exercises. This superior improvements may be attributed to the emphasis of Pilates on core strengthening, postural control, flexibility, controlled breathing and mind body coordination, which together contributes to improved physical functioning and pain management. Chair Aerobics exercises also showed beneficial effects in reducing dysmenorrhea symptoms increasing activity levels, particularly due to their low impact and easily accessible nature for sedentary working women. Thus, it can be concluded that both Pilates and Chair Aerobics exercises are effective non pharmacological interventions for the management of dysmenorrhea in desktop working women. However, Pilates exercises appear to be more effective in reducing pain and improving overall physical activity levels.

REFERENCES

1. Ju H, Jones M, Mishra G. The prevalence and risk factors of dysmenorrhea. *Epidemiologic reviews*. 2014 Jan 1;36(1):104-13.
2. Bhatt JP, Trivedi S, Mankad D. To compare the effectiveness of Pilates and chair aerobics on menstrual symptoms in females with primary dysmenorrhea – a pilot study. *Int J Health Sci Res*. 2024;14(1):65-71.
3. Ferries-Rowe E, Corey E, Archer JS. Primary dysmenorrhea: diagnosis and therapy. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2020 Nov 1;136(5):1047-58.
4. Berde SD, Yadav TS, Gosavi PM, Gijare SS. Effect of Core Strengthening Exercises & Chair Aerobic Exercises in Primary Dysmenorrhoea. *International Journal of Health Sciences*. 2019;3(6).
5. Sahin S, Ozdemir K, Unsal A, Arslan R. Review of frequency of dysmenorrhea and some associated factors and evaluation of the relationship between dysmenorrhea and sleep quality in university students. *Gynecologic and obstetric investigation*. 2014 Aug 20;78(3):179-85.
6. Armour M, Parry K, Manohar N, Holmes K, Ferfolja T, Curry C, MacMillan F, Smith CA. The prevalence and academic impact of dysmenorrhea in 21,573 young women: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of women's health*. 2019 Aug;28(8):1161-71.
7. Guimarães I, Póvoa AM. Primary dysmenorrhea: assessment and treatment. *Revista Brasileira de Ginecologia e Obstetrícia*. 2020 Sep 25;42:501-7.
8. Joshi T, Kural M, Agrawal DP, Noor NN, Patil A. Primary dysmenorrhea and its effect on quality of life in young girls. *Int J Med Sci Public Health*. 2015 Mar 1;4(3):381.
9. Matsumura K, Tsuno K, Okamoto M, Takahashi A, Kurokawa A, Watanabe Y, Yoshida H. The Association between the Severity of Dysmenorrhea and Psychological Distress of women Working in Central Tokyo—A preliminary study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2023 Nov 5;20(21):7021
10. Khadiga S, Eman M, Mohamad F, Asmaa M. Effect of Pilates exercise on primary dysmenorrhea. *The Medical Journal of Cairo University*. 2019 Mar 1;87(March):1187-92.
11. El Nahas EM, Atia DT, Hassan MH, Abd El AA, Sae'd Mahmoud SM. Effect of pilates exercise versus yoga on primary dysmenorrhea in adolescent girls. *SPORT TK-Revista EuroAmericana de Ciencias del Deporte*. 2024 Feb 22:5-.
12. Soni P, Desai D. Effectiveness of Pilates and Self-Stretching Exercise on Pain and Quality of Life in Primary Dysmenorrhea”—A Comparative Study. *Indian Journal of Physiotherapy & Occupational Therapy Print-(ISSN 0973-5666) and Electronic—(ISSN 0973-5674)*. 2021 Jun 9;15(3):129-38.
13. Mahvash N, Eidy A, Mehdi K, Zahra MT, Mani M, Shahla H. The effect of physical activity on primary dysmenorrhea of female university students. *World Applied Sciences Journal*. 2012;17(10):1246-52.
14. Sakpal S, Patil C. Efficacy of chair aerobics and progressive muscle relaxation in primary dysmenorrhea. *Journal of Coastal Life Medicine*. 2023;11(2):1511-1516.

HOW TO CITE: Lawrence Fernandes*, Effect of Pilates Vs. Chair Aerobics on Physical Activity in Desktop Working Women with Dysmenorrhea, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (7), 1365-1372. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21127025>

